

second week of Oct was accompanied by high wind velocity. We assessed the loss in yield among cultivars of different maturity groups.

Maximum yield loss was 55% in IET7251 — the crop lodged 1 wk before flowering — followed by Sugandha, which lodged at booting (see table). Among the semidwarfs, maximum yield loss was in Radha that lodged 1 wk before flowering, followed by Pankaj that lodged either at flowering or at booting. Minimum yield loss was in Sujata that lodged 10 d after flowering. □

Effect of time of lodging on rice yields.

Variety	Duration (d)	Growth stage at lodging	Yield (t/ha)		Loss ^a (%)	
			Lodged	No lodging		
<i>Dwarf (high yielding varieties)</i>						
Pankaj	155-160	Booting	3.5	6.5	46.8	e
Pankaj	155-160	Flowering	3.5	6.7	47.4	e
Radha	155-155	1 wk before flowering	3.1	6.2	49.9	f
Radha	150-155	1 wk after flowering	4.7	6.1	23.6	b
Sujata (BG90-2)	135-140	At flowering	3.5	5.4	35.7	c
Sujata (BG90-2)	135-140	10 d after flowering	4.4	5.2	18.2	a
Sita	135-140	1 wk after flowering	3.2	5.4	41.0	d
Sita	135-140	2 wk after flowering	3.2	5.4	41.6	d
<i>Tall plant type</i>						
Sugandha	Photoperiod sensitive	Booting	1.5	3.3	54.3	g
ET7251	155-160	1 wk before flowering	2.2	4.8	55.1	g

^a Values followed by identical letters are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

Seed dormancy in some short-duration rices

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We assessed seed dormancy in 11 traditional rice varieties and 14 promising short-duration (90-110 d) breeding lines grown during aus (Mar-Sep), when preharvest seed sprouting in the field often follows monsoon rains. Seeds collected 30 d after flowering, coinciding with peak monsoon months, were dried to 13-14% moisture content. Germination at harvest and length and intensity of dormancy were measured. Dormancy intensity was determined by the time necessary to break dormancy with 50 °C heat treatment for 4 d. Dormancy length was days to attain 80% germination under ambient conditions.

Dormancy was 15-44 d in the traditional varieties and 27-54 d in the breeding lines. Many traditional varieties had strong seed dormancy; all the breeding lines except CR289-1208

Seed dormancy of 25 shortduration rices. Chinsurah, India.

	Germination (%) after 4 d heat treatment at 50° C	Dormancy	
		Intensity ^a	Period (d)
<i>Traditional</i>			
Bhutmuri	24	MD	30
Harimandir	nil	SD	40
Orissa aus	2	SD	40
Begunbichi	2	SD	42
Soni	78	WD	43
Panke	nil	SD	32
N22	2	SD	35
Baumal	32	MD	31
Joli	nil	SD	44
Juma	98	WD	41
China aus	100	WD	15
<i>Breeding lines</i>			
HPU741	74	WD	42
IR9708-51-1-2	72	WD	35
IR9729-67-3	88	WD	40
CR289-1208 (IET7255)	55	MD	54
Suweon	100	WD	28
BKNLR75091-CNT-B3 RST40-2-2	100	WD	37
IR8608-189-2-2-1-3	95	WD	30
Pusa 312	100	WD	38
OR165-93-15	78	WD	44
RP2086-74-6-1	100	WD	27
UPLRi7	90	WD	27
IR13204-24-16	90	WD	34
NSRP-1 Early	95	WD	30
RAU4045-10	85	WD	33

^a WD = weakly dormant, MD = moderately dormant, SD = strongly dormant.

(IET7255) were weakly dormant (see table). China aus attained 100%

germination after heat treatment and had very weak dormancy. □

Leaf chlorophyll content of submerged rice seedlings

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We assessed leaf chlorophyll content of seedlings of six rice varieties (B-9c-Md-3-3, CN540, CR126-42-1, FR13A, Mohon, and OC1393) grown in pots under submerged and nonsubmerged conditions.

Seedlings were raised in 25-cm-diam earthen pots at 50 seeds/pot with 8 replications. At 10 d after seeding (DAS), 4 pots/variety were submerged in 50-cm water for 10 d, then treated normally to 35 DAS. Leaf chlorophyll